

tion can lead to the identification of interaction variables and constraints to production. In instances where new production practices evolve (such as the introduction of high-yielding semidwarf rice varieties), producer surveys may point to the need for a refinement of recommendations.

Producers can use the results to compare their farm responses with those of others. Identification of the principal sources of variation will allow producers to focus on information that can provide a basis for refining their production practices. Producers' knowledge of the relationship between

production inputs and rice quality can be improved if research and extension specialists report yield and quality results from research and experimental trials and if more research is devoted to producer-controlled impacts such as postharvest handling. ■

Comparing methods of stability analysis in rice hybrids

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Yield heterosis in rice is reported to interact with environment. Identifying rice hybrids with stable performance is a prerequisite to successfully exploiting this technology over a large area. The popular parameter for selection of stable entries used by many breeders is the varietal mean averaged over locations. Another method is to rank entries for each location and then use mean performance of the rank to assess their potential. It is well known that genotype \times environment ($G \times E$) interactions

in multilocal yield trials and the comparison of cultivar means are not very useful. In addition, the mean and its ranks do not indicate the location-wise magnitude of differences between the test entry and the standard check against which selection is to be made. In recent years, many new methods have been proposed for stability analysis. We compared the following three methods with selection based on the experimental mean: 1) a superiority measure of a cultivar, 2) nonparametric measures of phenotypic stability, and 3) relative yield as a measure.

We used the grain yield data of a hybrid rice trial conducted over 12 locations in the 1994 wet season for the study, and calculated the rank correlation (r_s) between methods. The results showed that selection based on means

of entries was closer to method 3, $r_s = 0.99$, followed by the superiority measure ($r_s = 0.95$). The ranking based on nonparametric measure was not related to the mean. Of the three methods used, the superiority measure was found to be useful for identifying stable hybrids. We analyzed the yield data from six trials conducted during 1994-95 to ascertain the usefulness of the superiority measure for identifying stable hybrids. The best-yielding hybrid was found to be the most stable. The superiority measure—as a method—is simple, convenient, and quite useful, because it uses only one parameter, which makes comparison among test genotypes easier. This method also indicates the highest yielding genotype, one that could be recommended for the whole region. ■

Education and communication

Role of voluntary agencies in popularizing hybrid rice production in India

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The Sri Aurobindo Institute of Rural Development, Gaddipalli, a nonprofit-oriented, nonsectarian, voluntary, and autonomous organization was established in 1973. A Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK) was started in 1985 with

funds from the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR). This KVK was judged as the best among 261 KVKs in the country during 1994-95. Nalgonda District is in the southern Telangana zone of Andhra Pradesh. This is a rural district and 88% of the population depends on agriculture. Hybrid rice in China on a large scale proved to have a more than 25% yield advantage over conventional pureline varieties. The wide adaptability of rice hybrids has produced increased rice production and productivity in China since the mid-1980s. This success prompted ICAR to accelerate research on hybrid rice, through an ICAR-

UNDP-funded project in India. This research network project involved 12 research centers (two lead, seven associate, and three strategic centers) and state seed production agencies located in the target environment. Through this network, several rice hybrids were developed and released for commercial cultivation. To popularize hybrid rice production on a large scale, the Sri Aurobindo Institute developed an integrated project that involved adaptive research at the institute farm; on-farm testing in farmers' fields; layout demonstrations on hybrid rice seed production; production and distribution of good quality hybrid rice